

FAIRY TALES AS A PHENOMENON THAT PLAYS AN ESSENTIAL ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE INTELLECT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. This paper is intended to reveal the importance of fairy tales and give some advice and recommendations for parents to select the fairy tales, which are suitable ones for the age of their kids.

Keywords: fairy tales, fantasize, speech, plot, the magical action, character, stories, folklore, hero.

СКАЗКИ КАК ЯВЛЕНИЕ, ИГРАЮЩЕЕ СУЩЕСТВЕННУЮ РОЛЬ В РАЗВИТИИ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ

Аннотация. Эта статья призвана раскрыть значение сказок и дать советы и рекомендации родителям по выбору сказок, подходящих для возраста их детей.

Ключевые слова: сказки, фантазия, речь, сюжет, волшебное действие, персонаж, рассказы, фольклор, герой.

Introduction

A fairy tale is a way by which parents can interest a child to produce an educational effect on him and solve any physiological problem. Fairy tales appeal to both the younger generation and the older, they can bring the child together spiritually and reveal his inner world. This is the first small safe life lessons. With the help of fairy tales, the child learns what is «good» and what is «bad». Fairy tales play the significant role in the development of the mind and intellect of children, children who read fairy tales from an early age begin to speak faster, they are able to think and analyze quickly.

Methodology

According to psychologists, preschool children have difficulty distinguishing reality from fiction, because too their whole life takes place in the world of concrete things: here is the bed, toy, mom, milk in a cup. The child understands that there are things out of his field of vision, for example, a dacha or mother's work, but you can come to the dacha or mother's work, they really exist. And where is the Sunny City in which Dunno lives or the Magic Forest is difficult for a child to imagine. Therefore, the magical action of fairy tale takes place right, where the mother reads this fairy tale and the child perceives this fairy tale as a reality, for example, asks not to read further, if he is scared.

Reading a fairy tale expands the child's vocabulary and develops his intellectual ability and also contributes to the development of speech. Listening to a fairy tale, the child gets acquainted with folklore in particular with proverbs and sayings. It is coincidence that speech therapists and teachers use fairy tale therapy when working with children, who have a delay in speech. With the help of fairy tales, the child develops fantasy. When reading a fairy tale, the kid puts himself in the place of some hero and wants to accomplish a feat, for example, save the

Snow White from her evil stepmother or go to the Emerald City and meet many friends. Psychologists say, that fantasy is considered the most important aspect for the development of speech and that it is very useful to fantasize.

The choice of a favourite fairy-tale character by a child gives parents reason to think about children's problems and fears. For example, if your favourite hero is the Ugly Duckling, you should think about and find out if your child is the subject of attacks and ridicule in the children's team, does he feel lonely, not everyone else. If the favourite hero is Dunis - this is also a reason to think about, why your child likes a lazy, stupid and sloppy character.

Fairy tales are the first lesson of morality. The heroes of fairy tales are endowed with courage, honesty, conscience, thanks to these heroes, it becomes easier for the child to learn, that good is stronger than evil and that evil will always be punished, and this, of course, will affect the future of the child, he will begin to think positively and will follow the path of good.

Recommendations

At the age of 2 to 3.5 years - classic children's simple repetitive plot: «Kolobok», «Teremok», «Repka».

After some time, you can proceed to longer and more meaningful tales of: «The three little pigs», «Little red riding hood».

At the age of 3, the child becomes aware of «his own self». For a three-year old baby, the presence in the fairy tales of such a role model hero preferably (with the same sex with him), is mandatory.

At the age of 3-5 years, it is important to select fair-tales, in which it is clear who is good, where is good and where is evil.

For preschool children (5 -6 years old), offer to read children detective stories of Nikolai Nosov's stories.

An excellent technique is to compose with the child. In this case, the educational effect will be stronger, because it will be directed to a specific child, taking into account his character and the problem, that needs to be solved.

Conclusion

Fairy tales are, first of all, a way to fantasize, speak and analyze. Adults, like children, love to listen and read fairy tales along with them. Every child is looking forward to hearing a new dairy tale from their parents, it does not matter from mother or from father, but the child is most eager to hear it from mother because mothers read so beautifully with accents and good diction and you will feel as if you are in the fairy tale and you are the main character, but the fathers also read the fairy tale well, even if a little serious. The same fairy tale can be read to a child many times, this will help him understand its meaning and plot.

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